

VOLUME-2

ISSUE № 1 2024

SCIENTIFIC-THEORETICAL JOURNAL

INTERNATIONAL EDUCATION RESEARCH

ISSN: 2181-4279

RESEARCH
ACADEMY

1/2024

INTERNATIONAL EDUCATION RESEARCH

SCIENTIFIC-THEORETICAL JOURNAL

XALQARO TA'LIM TADQIQOTLARI

ILMIY-NAZARIY JURNAL

МЕЖДУНАРОДНЫЕ ОБРАЗОВАТЕЛЬНЫЕ ИССЛЕДОВАНИЯ

НАУЧНО-ТЕОРЕТИЧЕСКИЙ ЖУРНАЛ

Founder:
LLC "Academy of Educational
Research"

Scientific-theoretical journal
1/2024

**INTERNATIONAL EDUCATION
RESEARCH**

Director:
D.A.Mamajonov

Editor-in-Chief:
S.T.Turgunov

Associate Editors:
M.Y.Sulaymonov
B.J.Urinov
S.X.Mutalov

The journal was registered by the Agency of Information and Mass Communications under the Administration of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan on January 20, 2023 as a mass media under the № 059 413

When using materials published on the pages of the journal, it is necessary to indicate that they are taken from the scientific-theoretical journal "International education research". The editors have no obligation to review and return the submitted articles. The author is responsible for the facts and information provided in the article. All articles placed electronically on the journal's website are considered published and are considered copyrighted.

Turgunov Sobiikhan Tashpolatovich

Editor-in-Chief

Rector of Namangan State University, doctor of pedagogical sciences, professor

Sulaymanov Mominjon Yusubjonovich
Deputy editor-in-chief
Namangan State University associate
professor, candidate of philological sci-
ences

Urinov Baxrom Jamoliddinovich
Deputy editor-in-chief
Senior teacher of Namangan State
University

Editorial board

Askarova Ogilkhan Mamashakirovna
Chairman of the editorial board
Professor of Namangan State University,
Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences

Boyboboyev Baxodir Gulamovich
Deputy Chairman of the Editorial Board
Namangan State University Associate
Professor, Candidate of Pedagogical
Sciences

**Kadir Khanov Murodkhan
Rashidkhanovich**
Namangan State Pedagogical Institute
vice-rector for educational affairs, candi-
date of chemical sciences, associate
professor

Honkeldiyev Sher Hakimovich
Professor of Fergana State University,
doctor of pedagogical sciences

Hasanjon Rozibobo Shomurodzoda
Professor of International University of
Foreign Languages of Tajikistan named
after Sofim Ulugzoda (Tajikistan)

Larisa Nikolaevna Lazutkina
Ryazan State University Vice-Rector for
Educational Affairs, Doctor of Peda-
gogical Sciences, Professor (Russia)

Tojiboyev Soyib Samijonovich
Professor of Uzbekistan State University of
Physical Education and Sports, Doctor of
Pedagogical Sciences

**Egamberdiyeva Turgunoy Akhmadja-
novna**
Professor of Fergana State University,
doctor of pedagogical sciences

Akramov Abdumalik Abdumutalovich
Deputy of the Legislative Chamber of the
Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan,
Doctor of Pedagogy, Professor

Baltabayeva Aida Tinaybekovna
Professor of Kyrgyz-Uzbek International
University named after B. Sidikov, doc-
tor of philosophy (Kyrgyzstan)

Ibragimova Gulsanam Nematovna
Tashkent State Pedagogical University
named after Nizomi, professor, doctor of
pedagogical sciences

Erkabayeva Nigora Shermatovna
Associate Professor of Kokan State
Pedagogical Institute, Doctor of Peda-
gogical Sciences

Artikova Muhaiyokhan Botiraliyeva
Professor of Andijan State Pedagogical
Institute, Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences

Zamilova Rimma Ramilevna
Professor of Namangan State Universi-
ty, doctor of philosophy

Panjiyev Kurbanniyoz Berdievich
Professor of Tashkent State Pedagogical
University named after Nizami, Doctor of
Pedagogical Sciences

Abdullayev Abduvali
Professor of Fergana State University,
Candidate of Pedagogical Sciences

Ulukhujayev Narzullokhan Ziyovadinovich
Namangan State University Associate
Professor, Candidate of Pedagogical
Sciences

Tokhtaboev Nizomjon Tursunaliyevich
Director of the Fergana branch of
Uzbekistan State University of Physical
Education and Sports, Doctor of Peda-
gogical Sciences, Professor

Shukurov Kamoliddin Elbobo ugli
Associate Professor of Tashkent University
of Information Technologies, Doctor of
Philosophy in Technical Sciences (PhD)

Akmalova Dildora Tokhirova
Associate Professor of Namangan
State University, Doctor of Philosophy
in Pedagogical Sciences (PhD)

Tashnazarov Djasur Yuldashevich
Associate Professor of the Institute of
Physical Education and Sports Scientific
Research, Doctor of Philosophy in Peda-
gogical Sciences (PhD)

Saidakbar Mutalov

PhD researcher of Namangan State University

E-mail: saidakbarmutalov@gmail.com**THE SYSTEM OF COMPETENCES ON THE DEVELOPMENT OF STUDENTS' LEADERSHIP SKILLS**DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11115895>

Abstract: This article presents comparative analysis of structural components and personal qualities of students' leadership skills, issues related to clarifying the important characteristics of leader-specific competencies and scientific views on the competence system for developing students' leadership skills.

Key words: higher education, student, leader, leadership skills, competence, analysis, education, education, system.

Introduction

It is known that there are different forms of leadership evidently in the nature of any student at a higher education institution. Sometimes such abilities, skills and individual qualities are hidden. Regardless of the level of student leadership, it is important to develop the existing socio-psychological knowledge, inculcate the necessary skills in their minds, and increase the competence of leadership and management so that students can continue their professional career as specialized leaders based on the theoretical knowledge and experience they have acquired in the university.

Our country have been carrying out further reforms on improving the quality of education in higher education institutions, using advanced foreign experiences, and using modern pedagogical technologies and innovative approaches effectively in teaching subjects. Increasing social activity of students, developing communicative qualities and leadership skills, formation of management competencies based on acceptable forms and methods of education are core issues in current pedagogical processes.

Therefore, it is essential to pay attention to the development of personal and social qualities of students and improving them as a perfect person is one of the important factors of revealing their leadership ability. In this regard, first of all, a person needs to have the following social qualities in order to rise to the level of a person. These gener-

ally include individuality, character, activity, goal orientation, direction and a purpose [1; 62-p.].

Materials and Methods

The qualities of student's leadership skills are reflected in the views of Russian scientists A.N.Lutoshkin and L.I.Umansky as follows [2; 47-p.]:

- competence - the ability to perform certain tasks and organize work;
- social activity - the ability to overcome the problems that have arisen, to be persistent;
- initiative - manifestation of special creative activity, promotion of ideas and proposals;
- perseverance - willpower, the ability to complete and complete tasks to the end;
- politeness - openness to others, politeness, ability to communicate with people;
- ingenuity - understanding the nature of situations and events, being able to see their causes and consequences, being able to find a solution;
- personal control - the ability to control and manage one's emotions and behavior in difficult situations;
- diligence - hard work, ability to perform complex tasks, endurance;
- observability - being able to record and remember important issues;
- independence - the ability to make independent decisions, find ways to complete tasks and take responsibility;
- organization - consists in submitting one-

self to the necessary work regime, planning one's activities, organizing work on the basis of consistency

The researches on clarifying the qualities related to leadership skills are very important in our country. In this regard, the scientist N.N. Djamilova, who conducted scientific research on the development of initiative qualities of students, explained the following competencies of leadership ability:

discipline - self-organization, sense of responsibility, willingness to obey personal goals and social instructions;

independence - the internal position of a person, the knowledge, skills and competences necessary to improve activities without the help of others, as well as the system of competencies;

diligence - to act on the basis of a specific goal in education, work and social activities, to mobilize one's energy and enthusiasm;

initiative - the ability to put forward new ideas and suggestions for success in educational and professional activities and to demonstrate them in practical activities;

goal orientation - the ability to clearly define one's life position and model ways to achieve one's goal;

responsibility - a complete understanding of the results of one's actions in accordance with the norms of behavior set by society, the desire to fulfill assigned tasks and tasks on time and smoothly;

diligence is a form of manifestation of a person's positive attitude to the process of labor activity, the integration of characteristics such as desire, will and activity;

sociability - readiness for joint, cooperative activities, openness to interpersonal relations, expression of inner feelings and aspirations on the basis of mutual respect and sincerity;

generosity - willingness to provide constant help, kindness and generosity, to sympathize with the achievements and sorrows of others;

determination - a willful quality of a person to show enthusiasm in finding a solution

to a problem based on making clear and correct decisions;

tolerance - respecting other people's worldview, religious beliefs, national and ethnic characteristics, traditions and rituals, not allowing discrimination and insults in dealings, considering humanity above all else, in the community as well as to comply with it in workplaces and neighborhoods [3; 28-p.].

Results and Discussions

As a result of the above theoretical analysis, literature review and empirical observations, we came to the conclusion that today's students' leadership skills consists of the following most important qualities and skills (see Table 1). Also, the student's leadership level and the characteristics that serve this process were clarified. Characteristics of the structural component of leadership ability serve as a criterion for determining the level of leadership development in students.

Leadership skills are mainly formed on the basis of systematically organized education. The development of students' leadership skills mean the ability to apply their knowledge, spiritual maturity, worldview, high behavior, individual qualities, professional skills and dominance characteristics to everyday life and activities, and their active attitude towards socio-historical processes. The structural components of the students' leadership skills were separated and the competencies were grouped (see Table 2).

The grouping of structural competencies of leadership skills help us to define the following important tasks:

1. To determine specific pedagogical and psychological measures for the development of students' leadership skills;
2. To create a model for developing students' leadership skills;
3. To properly organize the education of students' skills and strengthen the practical effectiveness of their existing qualities.

Table 1

The criterion of the level of leadership	Characteristics of the components of leadership skills
Knowledge	observant, deep thinker, knows a lot of interesting and useful things, always able to answer any question, intelligent, has his own point of view on any issue
Communicative	knows his team well and is active in relationships, has a wide range of communication with friends and acquaintances, always likes to be among people, is approachable, gets along quickly, can communicate effectively, can exchange verbal and non-verbal information
Self-control	can control himself, be a personal example, control his emotions in non-standard situations and does not give freedom to his actions, controls his activities, is disciplined
Initiative	does not wait for someone else's task or impulse, always independently puts forward new ideas and proposals, promotes promptness and activity in the performance of tasks, an innovator
Activity	an active participant in the social life of the team, enthusiastic, able to increase the activity of team members, likes to participate in events and projects
Self confidence	persistent, high ambition, has a firm position, loyal to his principles, always knows how to convince of the correctness of his point of view, never doubts his actions, never hesitates
Responsibility	is devoted to his duty, takes responsibility for any task, completes the work started in any case and cares about the result
Observability	can see far, analyzes the situation in the team, regularly pays attention to the behavior, social mood and relationships of team members, can evaluate processes
Management	has authority in the team, can follow behind, constantly develops knowledge and competences to maintain superiority, is a personal example, always gives hope, confidence and motivation to those around him, can evaluate the abilities of team members, his own achievement considers it the team's achievement
Diligence	approaches any work with enthusiasm and responsibility, endures long-term and physical work, never gets distracted by things outside of work, organizes planned work and strives for results
Independence	always performs assigned tasks personally, asks for help only in difficult situations, has high self-confidence
Organization	is active in organizational affairs, regularly participates in planned events and projects, organizes and manages his own and team activities, finds unusual solutions to problems
Persistence	relies on his will, is quick-witted, reacts to the situation quickly and makes decisions, gets the job done
Persuasiveness	self-confident, intelligent, manipulative, never questioning his actions, able to find good persuasive arguments and arguments, wide emotional range, able to follow
Emotional stability	an empathetic person, an optimist, always works with positivity, tries to ensure a strong psychological climate and mutual emotional attraction in the team, can find ways out of conflict situations, always shares motivation
Dominance	socially active, strives to be prompt in any situation, encourages and inspires his team members to be among the first, strives for healthy competition and to be superior to those around him, able to lead the team
Eloquence	knows the norms of literary language well, can speak in public in different audiences, expresses ideas beautifully, clearly and logically, follows speech etiquette, can focus the attention of the audience and affect them emotionally, has strong improvisation
Foresight	predicts future events (foresight), can realistically imagine the activities of the team in the near future, can assess the impact and consequences of changes and risks, can manage situations

Table 2
The system of competencies on the development students' leadership skills

Competence group	Structural competencies of leadership skills
Moral competencies	Civility, responsibility, self-control, self-awareness, hard work, nobility, being a personal example, honesty
Creative competencies	Creativity, intelligence, broad outlook, non-standard thinking, efficiency, ingenuity
Professional competencies	Management skills, theoretical and practical training, strategic thinking, team building and management, division of tasks, ability to make decisions in non-standard situations, time management, inspiration, discipline, determination,
Communicative competencies	Public speaking, tact, systematic thinking, logical coherent speech, speech culture, audience management, facilitation skills, communication skills, manipulative skills, charisma
Organizational competencies	Activity, organization, initiative, promptness, systematic analysis ability, diligence, social activity

Through leadership, students are instilled with the idea of achieving their goals, effectively using their internal capabilities, and becoming progressive in society based on their acquired competencies. Every person not only needs to satisfy his own internal motives and needs, but also deeply understands that he should be able to give trust and hope to others. Cognitive consciousness, heuristic knowledge, mental intelligence and communicative ability are strengthened based on the integration of his general ability [4; 68-p.]. Therefore, it is more effective to develop students' leadership skills and implement them on the basis of the foundations of higher education. All the qualities of the student are enriched through theoretical knowledge and necessary skills to become a real leader.

Conclusion

In pedagogical processes, the formation of the worldview of students, increasing their social activity is related to the educational process based on specific mechanisms. Strengthening the system of existing competences of leaders will contribute to their effective functioning as comprehensive specialists in various fields and sectors of the country and their formation as promising personnel in the future.

Therefore, today not only higher education institutions, but also primary organizations of the Youth Union of Uzbekistan operating in them, student councils, youth centers and clubs, as well as structures that

serve to increase the creative, social and spiritual activity of students in general. has important pedagogical functions. In fulfilling these tasks, the activity of higher education institutions based on mutual socio-pedagogical cooperation has a positive effect on the processes of strengthening the competencies that serve to develop the leadership ability of students. In addition, the socio-pedagogical environment and the above structures are generally responsible for the effectiveness of education in this direction.

References:

1. Ziyomammedov B. Pedagogik mahorat asoslari. – Toshkent: "TIB-Kitob", 2009. – B. 183.
2. Лутошкин А.Н. Как вести за собой. – М.: Просвещение, 1986. – С. 121.
3. Джамилова Н.Н. Педагогические механизмы развития инициативности у студентов педагогических вузов. ДИС...ДОКТ. пед. наук. – Ташкент, 2019. – 275 б.
4. Mutalov S.X. Talabalarda liderlik qobiliyatini rivojlantirishda xalq pedagogikasining tarbiyaviy-didaktik imkoniyatlari. "Zamonaviy tarbiyada xalq pedagogikasining o'rni" mavzusidagi xalqaro ilmiy-amaliy konferensiya. – Qarshi, 2022. – B. 162-168.
5. Mutalov S. K. Leadership in the Views of Eastern Thinkers Ability Development Issues //International Journal of Multicultural and Multireligious Understanding. – 2022. – T. 9. – №. 6. – С. 61-68.